

A NOTE ON TRICHLORO-MONOPYRIDINO-ANTIMONY COMPLEX

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Addition compounds of antimony chloride with ammonia and some organic amines are known (Schiff, *Annalen*, 1864, 131, 116; *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 805; *Compt. rend.*, 1905, 56, 1863). The preparation of a pyridine complex with antimony chloride, not recorded before, is described here.

The chemicals used were of Analar quality. A solid product contaminated with pyridine is obtained when saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride is mixed with pyridine. If however, a saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride is mixed with ether and the homogeneous solution, thus obtained, is treated with dilute ethereal solution of pyridine with constant stirring, a white powder is obtained. The solid, thus prepared, was filtered, washed with ether till free from antimony chloride and dried in vacuum (H_2SO_4).

The compound does not hydrolyse easily in contact with water and is soluble in HCl (conc.). It is decomposed by caustic alkali and a small amount of oily substance, probably pyridine, is obtained. On heating it evolves pyridine vapour.

The antimony content of the substance was determined by standard potassium bromate, and chloride content by Volhard's method after decomposing the complex with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and filtering off the chloride from the insoluble oxide. Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl method. The results are: Sb, 39.65% (calc. for $SbCl_3 \cdot C_5H_5N$: Sb, 39.73); Cl, 34.03% (calc., 34.61); N, 4.20% (calc., 4.35).

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